

THE ROLE OF LITERARY AND ARTISTIC ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL GROUPS IN THE FORMATION OF COMMUNICATION CULTURE

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Abstract

The artistic and aesthetic development of preschool children is determined by the task of directed and consistent formation of the fundamentals of artistic and aesthetic culture in order to promote the formation of an aesthetic attitude towards the world in a child and the harmonization of the worldview - the worldview.

Artistic culture is a way of spiritual and practical development of the world and includes various types of artistic and creative activities: development of works of art; own participation in a certain type of activity; creating your own works of art; dissemination of artistic knowledge.

Keywords: literary and artistic activities, preschoolers, language, culture of communication, samples

1. Introduction

Activity is a relationship, a relationship between the organism and the environment, in which energy consumption takes place, with an adaptive purpose. In a narrower sense, by activity we understand the totality of external or mental behavior manifestations that lead to adaptive results. The activity represents the most natural and truthful way of externalizing and objectifying the internal psychic organization of man, of attesting the instrumental-creative, temperamental and characteristic valences of his personality profile.(Ețco, Fornea, Davidescu, Tintiuc, Daniliuc, Carăruș, 2007).

The literary-artistic education of preschoolers focuses on the formative dimension of the literary text, contributing to the familiarization of children with the structure of the Romanian language, with its richness and expressiveness, through the acquisition of new plastic words and expressions, rhyming and rhythmic constructions, sayings, proverbs and grammatical structures correct.

Communication between children in kindergarten is carried out with the help of language, which "is a specific form of human communication" (M. Roșca, 2022), and the acquisition his is gradually realized from the earliest age in the bosom of the family, without methodical or scientific guidance. Of particular importance in the study of language in the instructive-educational process is the adoption of an appropriate methodology that allows understanding how language is organized, structured and developed at this age. (Boscaiu, 1979).

2. Theoretical approaches regarding literary and artistic activities in preschool

The activity is the main form of organizing learning in kindergarten, with preschoolers. This is a fundamental kindergarten, with the help of preschoolers they develop knowledge, skills, skills, abilities, achieving the objectives and then forming the skills of the children according to the Curriculum.

Literary texts proposed for artistic literary activities must be correlated in relation to the age characteristics of preschoolers and their level of knowledge, so that they understand the literary work, the literary text and transpose it into new situations of experience, create new ones. experiences. The literary text is an important tool in the development of communication and oral expression.

The researcher C. Şchiopu states that the literary text is a text through which the author aims to impress and excite the readers, expressing his own thoughts, ideas and feelings, by using an artistic language, strongly marked by subjectivity (Şchiopu, 2010).

The literary text is an aesthetic object: a message of ideas, conceptions, feelings and is appreciated, first of all, for its artistic value. It means text plus aesthetic value. The aesthetic is therefore the fundamental value of literature and the one that gives it autonomy. The goal is to please the reader, to excite, to arouse aesthetic and artistic emotion.

Methodists G. Bărbulescu and D. Beşliu note that literary texts are fictions, even if they start from reality, which they more or less reflect. The imaginary character can only be established by referring to the communication situation in which it is placed. For a text to be considered literary it must:

- to convey an individual, subjective impression of reality;
- to reflect generally human ideas;

- to excite the receiver;
- to have a specific construction (conative language, lexical richness, polysemanticism, uniqueness, expressiveness) (Bărbulescu, Beșliu, 2009).

Literary reception is a complex psychic, intellectual and cultural-spiritual process and includes perception, imagination and artistic thinking, associated with language and communication.

Tales and stories are the most beloved guided activities in kindergarten, which satisfy children's need for knowledge and affection, develop positive behavioral states and manifestations, stimulate their imagination and create the optimal framework for communication.

Under the phonetic aspect, through specific activities, didactic games, exercise games, poems, stories, readings after pictures, etc., preschoolers learn to articulate correctly all the sounds of the language, their auditory discernment is perfected, in sensing the sound in the whole word or in syllabic groups, learning to divide words into syllables, improving and removing some deficiencies in the pronunciation of sounds (omissions, inversions, substitutions, extensions, etc.). Organizing these activities in the most pleasant way, makes the child's expression as relaxed as possible, giving the educator the opportunity to know the possibilities of verbal expression of each child, having the possibility of a tactful intervention in correcting possible minor mistakes or calling to the speech therapist.

From a lexical aspect, the preschool child's language is enriched in terms of active and passive vocabulary with common nouns, proper nouns, adjectives, cardinal and ordinal numerals, verbs, prepositions and conjunctions.

Language development in preschoolers is not limited only to phonetics, to the quantitative growth of vocabulary, but with the assimilation of the lexical fund, children also acquire the meaning of words and the grammatical structure

in a practical way in the living process of communication. (<https://www.scribub.com/gradinita/Rolul-activitailor-din-gradini> viewed 02.12.2022).

Cultivating language expressiveness is of great importance at preschool age. This involves observing the intonation, accent, rhythm, tone pauses and nuance of the voice during current speech or in the reproduction of fragments of a known literary text without deviations from the subject, repetitions or omissions, the correct rendering of the dialogue.

3. Research methodology

The experiment aimed at validating the level of formation of communication culture through literary and artistic texts in preschoolers and was focused on:

- series of principles, which can capitalize on the freedom of imagination and opinion of preschoolers, stimulating interest in knowledge, updating the experience of listening/listening to stories;

- quantifying the formative potential of literary and artistic texts, which is edifying if preschoolers are provided with the opportunity to analyze a fact/case, to make and argue decisions, to foresee their consequences. The exchange of feedback with colleagues, to revise a solution, the skills to carry out a task in a group, to use different learning strategies that contribute to the formation of the culture of communication;

- the activation of literary-artistic education in the process of interpreting a literary text, leads to the strengthening of one's own knowledge and experiences, to compare one's solution with the values, ideals, visions of others. This correlation generates an emotional attitude towards the respective modalities.

As criteria for validating the values of preschoolers' communication culture, the literary and artistic characteristics, demonstrated by preschoolers and presented in Table 1.1, served.

Table 1. Criteria for evaluating the culture of communication through literary and artistic texts in preschoolers:

Test / Criteria	Level
1. Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs - Brothers Grimm	
Observing the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work Discovering, exploring and following the rules in retelling the message of the literary work Characterization of the characters, identification of the relationships between the characters Enrichment of emotional affective and artistic experience to the message of the text The variety of expressive, aesthetic means and the volume of vocabulary Identifying new words/artistic expressions I play the opening and ending formulas of the stories	Advanced- A
Observe the partial facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work Discover and partially retell the message of the literary text Partially identifies unknown words It characterizes and partially identifies relationships between characters	Developing-D
He does not notice the facts and phenomena in the literary work He does not explore, he is not interested in the message of the literary work Identifies but does not characterize the characters in the text It does not suggest solutions to the problems raised in the text	Need Support-S
2. To cherries - Ion Creangă	
Observing the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work The discovery, exploration and accuracy of the retelling of the message of the literary work, as well as its clarity Identifying and enriching the vocabulary with new words	Advanced- A

<p>Characterization of the characters, identification of the relationships between the characters</p> <p>Enrichment of emotional affective and artistic experience to the message of the text</p> <p>Identifying and suggesting ideas, solutions for the problems faced in the text</p>	
<p>Partially observes the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work</p> <p>Discover and partially retell the message of the literary text</p> <p>Partially identifies unknown words</p> <p>It characterizes and partially identifies the relationships between the characters</p>	Developing-D
<p>He does not notice the facts and phenomena in the literary work</p> <p>He does not explore, he is not interested in the message of the literary work</p> <p>Identifies but does not characterize the characters in the text</p> <p>It does not suggest solutions to the problems raised in the text</p>	Need Support-S
3. Pinocchio - Carlo Collodi	
<p>Observing the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work</p> <p>Discovering, exploring, retelling the message of the literary work</p> <p>The variety of expressive, aesthetic means and the volume of vocabulary</p> <p>Characterization of the characters, identification of the relationships between the characters</p> <p>Enrichment of emotional affective and artistic experience to the message of the text</p> <p>Artistic and creative imagination in making/describing facts, events, characters</p>	Advanced- A
<p>Partially observes the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work</p> <p>Discover and partially retell the message of the literary text</p> <p>Partially identifies unknown words</p> <p>It characterizes and partially identifies the relationships between the characters</p>	Developing-D
<p>He does not notice the facts and phenomena in the literary work</p>	Need Support-S

<p>He does not explore, he is not interested in the message of the literary work Identifies but does not characterize the characters in the text It does not suggest solutions to the problems raised in the text</p>	
<p>4. Sleepy birds - M. Eminescu</p>	
<p>Great interest in hearing a text Observing the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work Expressive interpretation: with intonation, rhythm, pause, accent, intensity and timbre of the voice; pronounce the sounds of the Romanian language correctly Identifying artistic expressions in the text Enrichment of literary artistic experience to the message of the text Imagining characters, facts, actions and descriptions of nature</p>	<p>Advanced- A</p>
<p>Partially observes the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work Interpret the text/poem partially and with help He partially pronounces the sounds of the Romanian language Partially identifies artistic expressions, new words in the text Manifests some emotional states towards the taught text</p>	<p>Developing-D</p>
<p>Low interest in listening to a text Interpret only with support the text/poetry Does not identify artistic expressions / new words in the text It does not manifest any state or opinion of its own about the text</p>	<p>Need Support-S</p>
<p>5. What are you rocking... M. Eminescu</p>	
<p>Interest in hearing a text Observing the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work Expressive interpretation: with intonation, rhythm, pause based on phonemic hearing and correct pronunciation Identifying artistic expressions in the text Enrichment of the literary-artistic experience with the message of the text The use of verbal and non-verbal means</p>	<p>Advanced- A</p>
<p>Partially observes the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work Interpret the text/poem partially and with help He partially pronounces the sounds of the Romanian language</p>	<p>Developing-D</p>

Partially identifies artistic expressions, new words in the text Manifests some emotional states towards the taught text	
Low interest in listening to a text Interpret only with support the text/poetry Does not identify artistic expressions / new words in the text It does not manifest any state or opinion of its own about the text	Need Support-S
6. Who can know - Ana Blandiana	
Interest in listening to a text and understanding it Observing the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work Expressive interpretation: with intonation, rhythm, pause; pronounce the sounds of the Romanian language correctly Identifying artistic expressions in the text Enrichment of the literary-artistic experience with the message of the text Reasoned expression of one's own moods/opinions, using language; generating ideas	Advanced- A
Partially observes the facts and phenomena that occur in the literary work Interpret the text/poem partially and with help He partially pronounces the sounds of the Romanian language Partially identifies artistic expressions, new words in the text Manifests some emotional states towards the taught text	Developing-D
Low interest in listening to a text Interpret only with support the text/poetry Does not identify artistic expressions / new words in the text It does not manifest any state or opinion of its own about the text	Need Support-S
7. The lazy bumblebee - E. Farago	
Argued expression of one's post-reading moods/opinions, using the language; The use of verbal and non-verbal means Imitation of states: anger, surprise, joy, sadness, fear Experimenting, solving problem situations, generating ideas, Imagining characters, facts, actions and descriptions of nature Imitation of states: anger, surprise, joy, sadness, fear	Advanced- A
Expresses some moods or personal opinions about the text/work	Developing-D

<p>Uses some verbal and non-verbal means Experiment and solve some problem situations in the opera Describes some actions or deeds of characters or descriptions of nature</p>	
<p>It does not express its own opinion or state about the text/work Low use of verbal and non-verbal means It does not present solutions to problem situations with only support Describe some actions or facts only with the support of the educator</p>	<p>Need Support-S</p>
<p>8. The petted girl - O. Cazimir</p>	
<p>Argued expression of one's post-reading moods/opinions, using the language; The use of verbal and non-verbal means; Using an intonation with rhythm, accent, intensity appropriate to the poem; Imitation of states: anger, surprise, joy, sadness, fear; Experimentation, solving problem situations, generating ideas; Imagining characters, facts, actions and descriptions of nature</p>	<p>Advanced- A</p>
<p>Express some moods or personal opinions about the text/work Uses some verbal and non-verbal means Experiment and solve some problem situations in the opera Describes some actions or deeds of characters or descriptions of nature</p>	<p>Developing-D</p>
<p>It does not express its own opinion or state about the text/work Low use of verbal and non-verbal means It does not present solutions to problem situations with only support Describe some actions or facts only with the support of the educator</p>	<p>Need Support-S</p>

4. Research results

By capitalizing on the communication culture formation strategies for preschoolers through literary and artistic texts, we find that we have competent children to explore a literary text, in the context of capitalizing on communication in relation to the transmitted message. The high-level preschooler: confirms the

presence of emotional-affective reporting to the message of the text heard by extracting essential and detailed information; the characterization of the characters denotes the detection of attributes, stylistic figures in the presented text; the exposure of personal opinions, experienced emotions, the externalization of the soul and moral characteristics of the characters, valued through language, intonation, expressiveness confirm the evaluation of literary texts; logically argue literary preferences. The preschooler with an average level: partially expresses his opinion regarding the problem of the text, without the presence of creative ideas; he has an unargued position towards his own states; the lack of communication prevents the valorization of the artistic language in order to form the culture of communication through literary texts, resorting to the phrases impressed me, I like; it usually reproduces the story extracted from the literary text and does not pretend to be produced as a valorizer; it does not discern the comprehensive substratum of the literary text. The preschooler with a low level is considered by the lack of opinion towards the problematic of the work, the soul and moral qualities of a character; has an unargued position vis-à-vis his own states; the lack of communication blocks the exploitation of artistic language for the purpose of forming the culture of communication compared to the literary text; he notices no more than the pattern of the literary text, the stylistic expressions or the mode of communication.

The table below shows the criteria for evaluating the culture of communication in the experimental group, as well as the difference, in percentages, from the initial/finding phase and the final/control phase for preschoolers at the advanced level.

Table 2. Evaluation criteria of the elements of communication culture through literary and artistic activities in the initial phase (finding) and the final phase (control phase) in the experimental group, advanced level:

Nr.	Criteria for evaluating the culture of communication through literary and artistic activities	The initial phase of the experiment. (%)	The final phase of the experiment. (%)	The difference%
1.	Reception and narration of the text	16,36	43,63	27,27
2.	Storytelling and text comprehension	12,62	40	27,38
3.	Narration in fragments of the text	16,36	41,81	25,45
4.	Understanding and reciting poetry	18,18	40	21,82
5.	Expressive recitation and acquisition of artistic words from poetry	20	34,54	14,54
6.	Understanding and expressing emotions in fables	12,72	47,27	34,55
7.	The artistic expressiveness of the poem-fable	16,36	45,45	29,09
8.	Expressive recitation of poetry	14,54	47,27	32,73

Fig.1. Evaluation criteria and the difference from the experimental group, both in the ascertainment stage and the final/control stage - advanced level

Analyzing the results obtained in the control stage, the experimental group obtained a percentage of 43.63% in the control stage and 16.36% in the observation stage for the criterion of receiving and narrating the text; advanced level; the difference of 27.27% represents the fact that the preschooler is interested in the heard text, narrates the text, discovers, explores and respects the rules in retelling the message of the literary work. On the criterion of telling stories and understanding the text, 40% in the control stage compared to 12.62% in the detection stage, preschoolers from the advanced level enriched their literary and artistic experience, characterized the characters and identified the relationship between them, pronounced the sounds of the language correctly Romanian. According to the criterion of narrating the text in fragments, 25.45% in the final stage compared to 16.36% in the observation stage, the experimental group at an advanced level of narrated the text in fragments, understood the text, identified the new words and used them in new situations; they played the beginning and end formulas of the stories. At the criterion of understanding and reciting the poem 40% in the final stage compared to 18.18% in the observation stage, those from the advanced level, the experimental group understood and recited the poem logically, identified the new and/or unknown words and used in new contexts, they correctly used the intonation, pause, rhythm and showed interest in the poetry heard. At the criterion of expressive recitation and acquisition of artistic words from poetry, 34.54% at the control stage, the experimental group compared to 20% of the observation stage, preschoolers recited expressively, respecting the intonation, pause, rhythm of the poem; they learned artistic words from the text and used them in new situations, they

respected the established rules for reciting poetry. On the criterion of understanding and expressing emotions from the fable, 47.27% at the control stage compared to 12.27% at the observation stage understood the meaning, the moral of the text heard; they expressed their own opinion about the events, the actions in the text, they argued their own state, using the language. On the criterion of artistic expressiveness of the poem-fable 45.45% at the control stage, the experimental group, the advanced level compared to 16, 36% of the observation stage recited the poem-fable correctly and beautifully, they used verbal and non-verbal means, and they expressed their own opinion about the events in the text, they respected the rules and the clarity of reciting the poem. At the criterion of expressive recitation of the poem, 47.27% at the control stage, the experimental group, the advanced level compared to 14.54% at the observation stage, recited the poem logically, learned artistic words from the text, used the appropriate intonation of the text, they presented the states of anger, joy, sadness in the text, they expressed their own opinion about the actions in the text, they found solutions to the problems raised in the text, they described the image in the poem, enriching their emotional affective and artistic experience with the message of the text .

From the data collected, from both evaluations (finding and control), it was observed that the highest degree of difficulty regarding the achievement of communication culture training tasks was found in the process of expressive recitation and the acquisition of artistic words from poetry, as well as in dividing words into syllables and recognizing the initial sound in a word, where the lowest values were recorded, in terms of performing the tasks of artistic expressiveness of poetry and expressing emotions, high values were recorded.

The increase in the formation of the culture of communication in the preschoolers in the experimental group is obviously of a higher level than that of

the preschoolers in the control group, so we can say that the experimental approach had beneficial effects on the students.

The results of the pedagogical experiment allow us to state that the level of communication culture among preschoolers in the experimental group increased considerably compared to the level of communication culture among preschoolers in the control group. This fact confirms the validity of the research hypothesis and the effectiveness of the methodology of forming the culture of communication through literary and artistic activities in preschoolers.

5. Conclusions

The application of various literary and artistic activities for the formation of the culture of communication in preschoolers is focused on the principles of literary-artistic education, which launch a system of values, outline the investigation of the scientific problem, ensuring its functionality through the necessary resources and tools, through the freedom of imagination and opinion, through stimulating the interest in knowledge, by updating the reading and life experience, by cultivating skills.

The training strategies stimulate preschoolers' interest in knowledge, motivate the activity of reading and interpreting literary texts, amplify the formation of communication culture through literary and artistic activities in preschoolers by activating the aesthetic and life experience in the process of interpreting the literary work, preschoolers being put in the situation of to call on one's own knowledge and experience.

In the framework of the experiment, various activities for the formation of the communication culture of preschoolers in relation to the literary work were implemented and capitalized, such as: activities in groups, in pairs, frontal,

individual, etc.; communication culture training strategies were developed/adapted and reported at the preschool level, aiming to obtain a preschooler able to understand what is read to him, capable of perceiving the world around him, analyzing, communicating and interacting with peers, expressing their thoughts, moods, feelings and opinions towards the read text.

The results obtained in the intervention phase demonstrate the effectiveness of the process of forming the culture of communication through literary and artistic texts, by accumulating the skills to reproduce correct and coherent messages, interpreting the texts objectively. The progress registered as a result of the experimental activities demonstrates a significant difference and an increase in the quantitative and qualitative weight of the experimental values obtained by the subjects from the experimental sample at the control stage, compared to the answers given by the subjects from the control sample, confirmed by carrying out the evaluation tests summative.

Through its programs, the kindergarten allows the passage of circles of words, clear and correct pronunciation, nuanced speech, reproduction of stories, poems, familiarization with the situation of communication, training and language cultivation. (Caillois,1975)

The purpose of any act of learning is the future usefulness of the results obtained. Learning doesn't just have to lead somewhere, it just has to allow easier progression to the next stage. (Planchard, 1976)

The literary-artistic development of preschoolers is carried out starting from an early age both in the family and in preschool institutions through various forms of activity. Within the literary-artistic activities, both the sensory development and the formation of the communication culture of preschoolers are achieved (Lavric, 1992). Thus, the literary-artistic activities of preschoolers represent a main means in the process of personality formation, a means of

educating feelings and aesthetic attitude towards everything that surrounds us, a means of aesthetic, moral and intellectual education.

The formation of the culture of communication is a priority objective in the development of speech at preschool and aims at the auditory perception of the speech of those around. At the preschool age, it is necessary to train preschoolers in the habit of differentiating the sound elements of speech (sounds, words, phrases, etc.), the development of phonemic hearing, the habit of training auditory attention, etc. (Harlan, 1992).

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